

Innovative technologies and practical implementation

Production of thin-walled unreinforced elements out of UHPC

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The following article describes the results of research and development carried out by Sistrom-company in the field of UHPC achieved with ordinary raw materials, but with the water cement ratio decreased down to 0.2. The aim of this article is to provide a theoretical foundation for the phenomenon of skyrocketing compressive strength of Sistrom-concrete that reaches 100 MPa within the first 24 hours of curing. After providing a theoretical analysis of this effect, the outstanding properties of Sistrom-concrete are exemplified with a number of implementations – unreinforced thin-walled products, including those made with flexible formwork.

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The contemporary architectural design often demands shapes of high geometric complexity to be imposed on elements made of various materials. Such materials must meet the general requirements of strength, durability, safety, aesthetic appearance, and cost effectiveness. The cladding elements of complex geometry can be fabricated from metal or polymers, but they are generally inferior to the durability and cost-efficiency of concrete. In addition, concrete surface may have different types of textures and colors embedded, therefore providing architects with ample opportunities to realize the most daring ideas.

Speaking about the standard concrete, it is hard to recognize the potential performance of this material. In normal conditions, concrete with average water-cement ratio slowly gains the strength and reaches the calculated strength in 28 days. As any conventional concrete, its tensile strength at bending is weak and withstands only up to 4 MPa. These facts result in the increased thickness and weight of a product. It is clear that these characteristics of conventional concrete make it difficult to manufacture light, thin-walled structures of a complex geometry.

Sistrom investigated the possibilities of producing concrete with strength properties high enough to produce unreinforced shells of 5 mm thickness, with dimensions reaching 2 x 0.5 m. In order to meet these requirements, concrete should have a compressive strength of 130 MPa and tensile strength in bending over 10 MPa. As well, it was important to achieve such strength in the first days of hardening. Nowadays, some laboratories achieve these properties by using special cements, special sand, numerous chemical additives, superfine densifying fillers such as microsilica suspension, etc. All these activities greatly reduce the economic efficiency of UHPC, reducing its affordability. Therefore the objective was to create an alternative type of UHPC using standard materials, to avoid the rise in cost of production. The second objective was to achieve the highest possible early strength of concrete under normal conditions of hardening. It is known that regular C30/40 concrete standard Portland cement concrete reaches its maximum strength of 40 MPa on the 28th day of normal hardening. Its 24-hours strength is about 25 % of the concrete grade and equals to 10 MPa. The latter requirement is due to the fact that for production of thin-walled constructions, the strength at the moment of demolding must be higher than 100 MPa - ten times the strength of a standard 24 hours-old concrete. The experience of these studies in field of UHPC have shown that the solution of this problem is quite realistic.

While pursuing the goal to cast 5 mm thick products, Sistrom has developed an UHPC based on fine-grain aggregates. Assuming that facing products should be provided in a wide range of colors, Sistrom has chosen white cement to be the binder. The resulting composition of Sistrom concrete consists of sand with fineness modulus 2.1, white Portland cement CEM I 52,5 and plasticizing additive Glenium 115. The proportions were selected based on the law of strength of concrete expressed in the generalized formula by B. G. Skramtayev:

$$R_b = A \cdot R_c(CW - 0,5) \quad (1)$$

where

R_b - compressive strength of concrete, MPa at 28th day;
 A - coefficient of aggregate quality, sand equals 0.6;
 R_c - grade (or activity) of cement. In this case it is 50 MPa.
 CW - cement-water ratio

It should be noticed that in some sources (1) for high-strength concretes it was proposed to adjust this formula. This might be reasonable for concrete on gravel or crushed stone without plasticizers, however, after extensive processing of the data obtained through experimental research work with high- and ultra-high-performance fine-grain concrete, Sistrom has reckon that in this case the formula (1) accurately describes the pattern of dependencies between concrete strength and water-cement ratio, and does not need any adjustments.

For the practical convenience, the cement-water ratio was replaced with ratio of water-cement. The above mentioned empirical formula (1) for this purpose can be presented in a simplified form:

$$R_b = 30/WC - 15 \quad (2)$$

where

R_b - compressive strength (MPa) in the age of 28 days of normal hardening;
 WC - water-cement ratio.

Test results of concrete samples with different water-cement ratios almost completely matched the indicators calculated according to the formula (2). It should be noticed that the rheological characteristics of the concrete mixture provide appropriate ductility and workability at these water-cement ratios.

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The highest strength of concrete was obtained at $W/C=0.2$, exceeding 130 MPa. At the same time during the first 24 hours of hardening the concrete gained 70 % of its maximum strength, on the third day – 90 % and on the seventh day it reached its maximum value of 100 %.

For comparison, the kinetics of strength growth of Sistrom-Concrete with $W/C=0.2$ and standard concrete C30/40 with $W/C=0.55$ during the first 7 days of hardening under normal conditions are shown in fig. 2. The graph illustrates that during the first day of hardening, Sistrom-Concrete has exceeded strength of a standard concrete C30/40 almost 9 times and reached its strength of approximately 100 MPa. The tensile strength in bending in daily age exceeds 10 MPa.

The analyses of experimentally obtained data on UHPC with decreased water-cement ratio of 0.2 almost completely coincide with the parameters calculated by the empirical formula of the law of water-cement ratio (fig.1). However, this concerns only the maximum strength characteristics of concrete. Theoretically, the gaining of extremely high strengths by concrete with decreased water-cement ratio could be explained by the high material density and minimum porosity. The gauging water is consumed without residue in the cement hydration process. In other words, from the very early stages the concrete remains free of mechanically bound water that could have created a directed porosity during the process of drying. Strictly speaking, the concept of drying is not relevant for concrete with $W/C=0.2$ because all the water in it is in a bounded state already after 24 hours. Of course, it is not only chemically bound water, but also physically associated, so-called bound-adsorbed water.

However, if the final indicated concrete strength corresponds to the calculations by the Skramtayev formula, the empirically obtained data of the kinetics of concrete curing requires further analysis and

explanation. Empirically obtained data of the physical characteristics and the mapping of kinetics of the strength gaining of concrete with low water-cement ratio have provided that, the maximum strength is reached on the 7th day, and not on 28th as was thought earlier. Furthermore, with the mapping of kinetics it has been captured that the major part – 75 % (equal to 100 MPa) of the grade strength was gained during the first 24 hours. To say it once again, a standard concrete at the same age gains not more than 25 % (equal to 10 MPa) of the grade strength in the same curing conditions. However, the final strength of the former concrete is 135 MPa which is only 3.5 times higher than the maximum strength of the latter, a standard C30/40 concrete. It should be noticed that cement and aggregate used for the two types of concrete were the same. Thus, it is not possible to explain this phenomenon solely by the density of material. What is the cause of the dramatic increase of strength in the first days of concrete curing? In order to answer this question, Sistrom has turned to the theory of hardening of cement, in-depth examination of the cement hydration process, being concerned of the influences of individual minerals on the speed of formation of the solid structure of concrete.

Ettringite is one of the most mysterious and contradictory minerals, which appears during the cement hydration. Due to its special property of sudden formation and equally sudden disappearance, some researchers consider it elusive. After its formation on the very first stages of concrete setting, ettringite absorbs water and increases in volume up to 2.5 times. This can cause a destruction of young cement stone – the effect known as sulphate corrosion of concrete. This is why constructors used to call ettringite a “cement bacillus” or “sulphate bacillus”.

Typically, the formation of primary ettringite happens in the reaction of calcium sulphate dihydrate with tricalcium aluminate and water:

The stability region in which ettringite can be formed is quite narrow, and corresponds to pH domain from 10.45 to 13.0. With ultra-low water-cement ratio, such as 0.2, the concentration of alkali $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the pore liquid during the process of lime dissolution promptly reaches the maximum values, thus interrupting the formation of ettringite in first hours of concrete curing. In addition, the little amount of water is also preventing an extensive formation of 32-hydrate ettringite.

Fig. 1: The dependence of strength of fine-grained concrete on water-cement ratio. Concrete with 1.5 % additive of Glenium 115. Hardening at +20° C.

Fig. 2: The kinetics of the strength gain of Sistrom-concrete with $W/C = 0.2$ in comparison with standard concrete C30/40 and $W/C = 0.55$

Fig. 3: Coffee table with 5 mm wall thickness made of Sistrom-concrete with the use of flexible formwork.

Fig. 4: Products made of Sistrom-concrete with cylindrical cross-section diameter of 20 mm.

From the authors point of view, the primary ettringite does not only regulate the setting of cement, but also slows down the subsequent hardening, blocking cement grains from access of water that results in a retarded of formation of strong and stable hydrated silicates and hydrated calcium aluminates. Through taking away the water that exceeds 20 % of cement mass, we will get a synergetic effect – a rapid growing of concrete strength in the first 24 hours. The conclusion out of this research is, that this effect is a configuration of three factors. The first is chemical: the reduction of ettringite volume at the stage of concrete setting and complete termination of formation in the next hours unlock the cement grains for access of water and facilitate the process of deep hydration in short time. The second is physical: decreased distance between cement grains due to reduced volume of gauging water provides conditions for hydrates to quickly merge into solid mass. The third is structural: the literal absence of free water in concrete eliminates the directional porosity caused by drying of concrete, leading to significantly reducing microcracks, low water adsorption (less than 0.15 %) and high freeze-thaw resistance (more than F500).

All the three factors work together and simultaneously contribute to the impact on the speed of concrete strength gain during the first 24 hours. In practice this theory resulted in the development of Sistrom-concrete, which underlies majority of Sistrom technological innovations, one of the most remarkable being "Marble-from-concrete".

For over 25 years Sistrom-company has been successfully developing new technologies for fabrication of extra-durable concrete cladding products of high aesthetic quality, offering a wide range of colors and textures, focusing on imitation of marble and granite. The collected knowledge and experience in work with Sistrom-concrete allows it to create new types of products, one of which being the thin-walled unreinforced panels in flexible formwork.

In the development of flexible formwork, Sistrom has experimented with PVC sheets (fig. 3) as well as PVC hoses (fig. 4) of various thickness and size. In every case the formwork was first filled with concrete in a flat, unrolled position, consolidated on a vibration table, and immediately bended and placed in supporting constructions to cure in the required shape. Considering the high strength of Sistrom-concrete it is possible to produce this objects with 5-10 mm thickness and demold it on the next day.

Fig. 5: Decorative panel made of Sistrom-concrete with sizes 2000x1000x15 mm. The thickness of colored concrete layer is 5 mm.

All innovative technologies by Sistrom are based on an intensive scientific research and experimentation. The keynote for all of them is the practical implementation in production lines. Sistrom-company provides training courses for clients interested in starting their own production of high quality concrete products.

The company supplies all the necessary equipment, including more than 500 types of unique molds for fabrication of all types of cladding and facing products.

■ Bibliography

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■ FURTHER INFORMATION

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Fig. 6: Further examples of products out of UHPC